

BIR ASOSLI KARBON KISLOTA PROPARGIL EFIRLARI VA ULARNING PIPERIDINLI HOSILALARINI ENERGIYA TEJAMKOR OLISH USULI VA TAHLILI

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ANNOTATSIYA. Ushbu maqolada bir asosli karbon kislota propargil efirlari hamda ularni piperidinli hosilalarini energiya tejamkor olish usullari keltirilgan bo'lib, bunda fizik-kimyoviy tahliliy tadqiqot natijalari keltirilgan.

ABSTRACT. The article presents methods for the preparation of propargyl esters of monocarboxylic acids and their piperidine derivatives, which present the results of physicochemical analytical studies.

Kalit so'zlar: bir asosli karbon kislota, propargil efiri, paraform, piperidin, N-amino(butin-2-il) hosilalari.

Keywords: monocarboxylic acid, propargyl ester, paraform, piperidine. N-amino (butyn-2-yl) derivatives

Kirish. Hozirgi vaqtda jahonda xalq xo'jaligining ko'plab sohalarda qo'llanilayotgan turli vositalarning, jumladan, metallar korroziyasi ingibitorlari, gerbitsid, insektitsidlar va farmatsevtik preparatlarni ishlab chiqarish yildan yilga ortib bormoqda [1, 3-5, 7]. Bunday birikmalar qatorida o'zida uch bog' tutuvchi turli xil sintetik moddalar va ularning modifikatsiyasi asosida sintez qilib olingan hosilalar muhim ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi [2,8].

Materiallar va metodlar. Propargil hosilalari asosida alifatik, aromatik va turli geterosiklik moddalarni sintez qilish mumkinligi, ushbu funksional guruhning keng qirraliligini ko'rsatadi. Propargil guruhli hosilalar orasida ko'plab biologik faol moddalarning borligi ushbu yo'nalishda tadqiqotlar olib borish naqadar dolzarb ekanligini bildiradi [6].

Aminometillash reaksiyasi tegishli efirlar, dietanolamin, paraformdan 1:1:1,5 mol nisbatdagi aralashmalarini erituvchi muhitida 6-8 soat 80-110 °C haroratda qizdirib olib borildi. Reaksiyada erituvchi sifatida toluol, asetonitril va 1,4-dioksanlardan foydalanildi. Katalizator sifatida esa mis tuzlaridan: mis(I)xlorid mis(II)xlorid va mis (II) asetatlardan foydalanildi. Reaksiya katalizatorlarning turli xil nisbatlari va xar xil vaqt davomiyligida etanol, asetonitril, 1,4-dioksan eritmalarining qaynash haroratida olib borildi. Eng yuqori unumga esa mis (II) asetat katalizatorligida 1,4-dioksanda 6-soat qaynatib olib borilganda erishildi.

Natijalar va muhokamalar.

4-(bis(2-gidroksietil)amino)but-2-in-1-il butirat sintezi (1). Yuqorida keltirilgan usul orqali 1.26 g (1.34 ml, $\rho=0.94$ g/ml, 0.01 mol) propargil butirat, 0.45 g (0.015 mol) paraform, 1.05 g (0.96 ml, $\rho=1.097$ g/ml 0.01 mol) dietanolamin, 0.05 g (0.27 mmol) mis(II) asetat va 25.0 ml 1,4-dioksan olindi. Massasi 2.05 g. 84% unum bilan mahsulot (1) olindi. $T_{qay}=172-174$ °C. (8 mm. sim. ust.) R_f 0.66 (sistema geksan:etilasetat – 5:1). 1H YaMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$): 0.88 (3H, t, $J=7.34$, CH_3 -), 1.32 (2H, m, CH_3-CH_2 -), 1.59 (2H, t, $J=5.88$, $-CH_2-CH_2$ -), 2.31 (2H, t, $J=7.28$, $-CH_2-CH_2-OH$), 2.44 (2H, t, $J=7.14$, $-CH_2-CH_2-OH$), 2.70 (2H, t, $J=5.26$, $-CH_2-N<$), 2.98 (2H, c, , $-OH$), 3.61 (4H, t, $J=5.20$, $-CH_2-CH_2-OH$), 4.65 (2H, t, $J=4.10$, $-O-CH_2$ -) ^{13}C YaMR ($CDCl_3$): 15.24, 21.11, 38.54, 48.78, 56.15, 60.21, 62.80, 85.47. 85.734, 170.11 IQ-spektr (KBr, ν , cm^{-1}): 2958 (CH_3), 2932, 2873 (CH_2), 1742 ($>C=O$), 1244 ($-C-N-$), 1166 ($-C-O-C-$), 1109 ($-C-OH$),

Olingan moddalarning tuzilishi IQ va 1H YaMR spektrlari natijalari orqali o'rganildi. Jumladan, 4-(bis(2-gidroksietil)amino)but-2-in-1-il butiratning 1H YaMR spektri tahlil qilinganda (1-rasm) moy kislota qoldig'idagi protonlar tegishli 0.88 (3H, t, $J=7.34$, CH_3 -), 1.32 (2H, m, CH_3-CH_2 -), 1.59 (2H, t, $J=5.88$, $-CH_2-CH_2$ -), m.u. sohalarda, molekula o'rtasidagi uch bog'ga qo'shni bo'lgan metilen guruhlari esa 2.70

(2H, t, J=5.26, -CH₂-N<), 4.65 (2H, t, J=4.10, -O-CH₂-) m.u. sohalarda ikki protonli triplet ko‘rinishida, dietanolamin qoldig‘idagi metilen guruhlar protonlari 2.31 (2H, t, J=7.28, -CH₂-CH₂-OH), 2.44 (2H, t, J=7.14, -CH₂-CH₂-OH), 3.61 (4H, t, J=5.20, -CH₂-CH₂-OH), m.u. sohalarda ikki protonli triplet hamda to‘rt protonli triplet holdida, dietanolamin qoldig‘idagi gidroksil guruhlar protoni esa 2.98 (2H, c, -OH), m.u. sohada 2 protonli singlet holdida namoyon bo‘lganligi kuzatildi.

Шомуродов А. T-21 1H_CDCD3_ 400 MHz

1-rasm. 4-(bis(2-gidroksietil)amino)but-2-in-1-il butirat ning ¹H YaMR spektri.

Ushbu moddaning IQ- spektri tahlil qilinganda, molekuladagi metil guruhiga (CH₃) xos tegishli tebranishlar 2958 cm⁻¹ sohada, metilen guruhiga (CH₂) tegishli tebranishlar 2932 cm⁻¹, 2873 cm⁻¹ sohalarda, karbonil guruhiga xos (>C=O) tebranishlar 1742 cm⁻¹ sohada, uglerod-azot oddiy bog‘iga (C-N) tegishli tebranishlar 1244cm⁻¹ sohada, uglerod-kislorod-uglerod (C-O-C) bog‘lariga tegishli tebranishlar esa 1166 cm⁻¹ sohada, uglerod-gidroksil guruh (-C-OH) bog‘lariga tegishli tebranishlar esa 1109 cm⁻¹ sohalarda yutilish chastotalariga ega bo‘lganini guvohi bo‘ldik. Qolgan yangi moddalarning ham tuzilishi IQ hamda YaMR spektrlari orqali o‘rganilib tahlil qilindi.

4-(bis(2-gidroksietil)amino)but-2-in-1-il valerat sintezi (2). Yuqorida keltirilgan usul orqali 1.40 g (1.52 ml, ρ= 0.92 g/ml, 0.01 mol) propargil valerat, 0.45 g (0.015 mol) paraform, 1.05 g (0.96 ml, ρ= 1.097 g/ml 0.01 mol) dietanolamin, 0.05 g (0.27 mmol) mis(II) asetat va 25.0 ml 1,4-dioksan olindi. Massasi 2.11 g. 82% unum

bilan mahsulot (2) olindi. $T_{qay}=176-178\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. (8 mm. sim. ust.) Rf 0.68 (sistema geksan:etilasetat – 5:1). $^1\text{H YaMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): 0.88 (3H, t, $J=7.18$, CH_3 -), 1.26 (4H, m, CH_3 - $(\text{CH}_2)_2$ -), 2.12 (2H, t, $J=5.36$, $-\text{CH}_2$ - CH_2 -), 2.46 (4H, t, $J=6.14$, $-\text{CH}_2$ - CH_2 -OH), 2.81 (2H, t, $J=6.18$, $-\text{CH}_2$ -N<), 3.06 (2H, c, , -OH), 3.58 (4H, t, $J=5.26$, $-\text{CH}_2$ - CH_2 -OH), 4.81 (2H, t, $J=5.41$, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$ -) $^{13}\text{C YaMR}$ (CDCl_3): 16.24, 22.65, 26.37, 38.35, 49.86, 58.04, 59.88, 61.16, 75.87, 85.48, 175.24. **IQ**-spektr (KBr, ν , cm^{-1}): 2961 (CH_3), 2923, 2867 (CH_2), 1742 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1243 ($-\text{C}-\text{N}-$), 1159 ($-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}-$), 1112 ($-\text{C}-\text{OH}$),

4-(bis(2-gidroksietil)amino)but-2-in-1-il kapronat sintezi (3). Yuqorida keltirilgan usul orqali 1.54 g (1.69 ml, $\rho=0.91\text{ g/ml}$, 0.01 mol) propargil valerat, 0.45 g (0.015 mol) paraform, 1.05 g (0.96 ml, $\rho=1.097\text{ g/ml}$ 0.01 mol) dietanolamin, 0.05 g (0.27 mmol) mis(II) asetat va 25.0 ml 1,4-dioksan olindi. Massasi 2.16 g. 80% unum bilan mahsulot (3) olindi. $T_{qay}=184-185\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. (8 mm. sim. ust.) Rf 0.69 (sistema geksan:etilasetat – 5:1). $^1\text{H YaMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): 0.87 (3H, t, $J=7.16$, CH_3 -), 1.22 (6H, m, CH_3 - $(\text{CH}_2)_3$ -), 2.15 (2H, t, $J=5.44$, $-\text{CH}_2$ - CH_2 -), 2.49 (4H, t, $J=6.16$, $-\text{CH}_2$ - CH_2 -OH), 2.83 (2H, t, $J=6.14$, $-\text{CH}_2$ -N<), 3.07 (2H, c, , -OH), 3.66 (4H, t, $J=5.28$, $-\text{CH}_2$ - CH_2 -OH), 4.76 (2H, t, $J=5.23$, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$ -) $^{13}\text{C YaMR}$ (CDCl_3): 15.21, 20.81, 25.74, 31.71, 38.36, 49.81, 57.26, 59.98, 60.86, 85.97, 84.69, 176.12. **IQ**-spektr (KBr, ν , cm^{-1}): 2961 (CH_3), 2926, 2874 (CH_2), 1751 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1241 ($-\text{C}-\text{N}-$), 1168 ($-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}-$), 1109 ($-\text{C}-\text{OH}$).

4-(piperidin-1-il)but-2-in-1-il butirat sintezi (4). Yuqorida keltirilgan usul orqali 1.26 g (1.31 ml, $\rho=0.96\text{ g/ml}$, 0.01 mol) propargil butirat, 0.45 g (0.015 mol) paraform, 0.85 g (0.99 ml, $\rho=0.862\text{ g/ml}$ 0.01 mol) piperidin, 0.05 g (0.27 mmol) mis(II) asetat va 25.0 ml 1,4-dioksan olindi. Massasi 2.00 g. 90% unum bilan mahsulot (4) olindi. $T_{qay}=126-127\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. (8 mm. sim. ust.) Rf 0.56 (sistema geksan:etilasetat – 7:1). $^1\text{H YaMR}$ (600 MHz, CD_3OD): 0.89 (3H, t, $J=7.15$, CH_3 -), 1.30 (4H, m, piperidin 3, 5- CH_2 -), 1.60 (2H, p, piperidin 4- CH_2 -) 2.31 (2H, kv, $J=7.43$, CH_3 - CH_2 -), 2.54 (2H, t, $J=4.81$, piperidin 2- CH_2 -), 3.32 (2H, t, $J=1.97$, $-\text{CH}_2$ -N<), 3.67 (2H, t, $J=4.77$, piperidin 6- CH_2 -), 4.70 (2H, t, $J=1.97$, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$ -) $^{13}\text{C YaMR}$ (CDCl_3): 15.24, 21.11, 38.54, 48.78, 56.15, 60.21, 62.80, 85.47, 85.734, 170.11 **IQ**-spektr (KBr, ν , cm^{-1}): 2958 (CH_3), 2932, 2873 (CH_2), 1742 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1244 ($-\text{C}-\text{N}-$), 1166 ($-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}-$), 1109 ($-\text{C}-\text{OH}$),

4-(piperidin-1-il)but-2-in-1-il valerat sintezi (5). Yuqorida keltirilgan usul orqali 1.40 g (1.48 ml, $\rho=0.942\text{ g/ml}$, 0.01 mol) propargil valerat, 0.45 g (0.015 mol) paraform, 0.85 g (0.99 ml, $\rho=0.862\text{ g/ml}$ 0.01 mol) piperidin, 0.05 g (0.27 mmol) mis(II) asetat va 25.0 ml 1,4-dioksan olindi. Massasi 2.10 g. 89 % unum bilan mahsulot (5) olindi. $T_{qay}=158-159\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. (8 mm. sim. ust.) Rf 0.54 (sistema geksan:etilasetat – 7:1). $^1\text{H YaMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): 0.88 (3H, t, $J=7.34$, CH_3 -), 1.32 (2H, m, CH_3 - CH_2 -

), 1.59 (2H, t, J=5.88, -CH₂-CH₂-), 2.31 (2H, t, J=7.28, -CH₂-CH₂-OH), 2.44 (2H, t, J=7.14, -CH₂-CH₂-OH), 2.70 (2H, t, J=5.26, -CH₂-N<), 2.98 (2H, c, , -OH), 3.61 (4H, t, J=5.20, -CH₂-CH₂-OH), 4.65 (2H, t, J=4.10, -O-CH₂-) ¹³C YaMR (CDCl₃): 15.24, 21.11, 38.54, 48.78, 56.15, 60.21, 62.80, 85.47. 85.734, 170.11 IQ-spektr (KBr, ν, cm⁻¹): 2958 (CH₃), 2932, 2873 (CH₂), 1742 (>C=O), 1244 (-C-N-), 1166 (-C-O-C-), 1109 (-C-OH).

XULOSA

Xulosa sifatida aytish mumkinki, ushbu ishda bir asosli karbon kislota propargil efirlari va ayrim ikkilamchi aminlar asosida yangi N-amino(butin-2-il) hosilalari sintez qilindi va ularning yuqori unum bilan chiqishi harorat, vaqt, katalizator va erituvchilarning tabiatiga bog‘liqligi aniqlandi hamda xususiy fizik kattaliklari, tuzilishi, tarkibi va tozaligi zamonaviy fizik-kimyoviy tadqiqot usullari orqali aniqlandi.

ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI:

1. Шомуродов А.И., Махсумов А.Г., Исмаилов Б.М. Реакция аминометилирования некоторых пропаргиловых эфиров насыщенных карбоновых кислот с диэтаноломином // Ж. Universum: химия и биология : электрон. научн. журн. (Москва) февраль 2023, часть 1, №2(104) - С.59-65. DOI - 10.32743/UniChem.2023.104.2.14927.
2. Djuraev A.D Yakubxodjaeva M.R. Synthesis of 1,2,3-triazoles based on propargyl ethers of carbamate // Catalysis and Reaction Engineering. -2020. –Vol. 2. –P. 2–5.
3. Janet Bahri, Remi Blicke, Bassem Jamoussi, Marc Taillefer and Florian Monnier. Hydroamination of terminal alkynes with secondary amines catalyzed by copper: regioselective access to amines. *Chemical Communications*.-2015. 51 (56). –P. 11210-11212
4. H. Sharghia, R. Khalifeha,b, F. Moeinia , M.H. Beyzavia , A. Salimi Benic and M.M. Doroodmand. Mannich Reaction of Secondary Amines, Aldehydes and Alkynes in Water Using Cu/C Nanoparticles as a Heterogeneous Catalyst. *Journal of the Iranian Chemical Society*, 8, S89-S103.
5. Li, Pin-Huaa WANG, Lei, Mercurous Chloride Catalyzed Mannich Condensation of Terminal Alkynes with Secondary Amines and Aldehydes. *Chinese Journal of Chemistry*, 2005, 23, PP.1076—1080.
6. Shomurodov A.I., Ismailov B.M., Maxsumov A.G. Mannix reaksiyasi asosida bir asosli karbon kislota propargil efirlarini piperidin bilan o‘zaro ta’sirlashuv reaksiyalari // “Innovations in Technology and Science Education”, 2023. April. 2-t. 9-s. Volume 2. Issue 9. – P. 765-772 (Xalqaro impact factor IF=5,305).

7. Шомуродов А.И., Махсумов А.Г., Исмаилов Б.М. Синтез производных N-диэтаноламино акрилоамида и его физико-химических свойств / 2-Международная конференция “Инновационные развитие нефтегазовой отрасли, современная энергетика и их актуальные проблемы”. – Ташкент, 2021. 29 октября. – С. 165-166.
8. Махсумов А.Г., Мухиддинов Б.Ф., Машаев Э.Э., Исмаилов Б.М., Хакимова Г.Р. Определение оптимальных условий синтеза путем математического моделирования синтеза МЭЭ-1 // *Universum: Химия и биология: электрон. научн. журн.*, Изд. «МЦНО», Москва-2024, №1 (115), ч.2, с. 5-11. **DOI - 10.32743/UniChem.2024.115.1.16555**